

‘Brahmatattva’

An Outlook of South Asian Iconology

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Abstract: Hinduism is an amalgam of several cults, *viśva-tattva* (*viśva* “all, universal”) and *viśva-devatās* (myriads of divinities). The *Śrītattvanidhi*, a *śilpa* digest of the 19th century, compiled by Kṛṣṇarāja Uḍaiyār of the Mysore royal house, visualizes a comprehensive picture of *viśvatattva* and *viśvadevatās*. We have systematically summed up ‘Brahmatattva-*nidhi*’ (Brahman, the Universal Man). Though the names of the divinities are Sanskritized, and many are renamed or recast in vernaculars, they are extracts from various layers of Indian culture from the pre- or proto-historic time (frozen in literature, folk and classical) to the high medieval period (*śāstras* and *āgamas*). The final output confirms the underlying philosophy in Hinduism that the so-called higher and folk had harmoniously amalgamated to make up a cosmopolitan religion. Multitudes of divinities (personified natural forces [Trees, Serpents, Rivers], Patriarchs, Sages [god-man], Scriptures, Directions, Planets or celestial bodies and so on) are catalogued herein that may be refreshing to informants on Indian lore. The compilations, *Sammlung Alice Boner Geschenk an das Museum Rietberg Zürich* and *Museum of Indian Art Berlin*, are on-hand reference books for *Brahmatattva-devatās*.

Keywords: *Śrītattvanidhi*; Brahman, Brahmā, *Brahmatattva*; Viśvadevatā; *śāstra*; folk.

The *Śrītattvanidhi* (STN) “Treasure-trove of the Philosophies of Sacred Images” is an encyclopedia on Hindu Iconography. The author, *rājaṛṣi*-Kṛṣṇarāja of the Maiśūru (Mysore) Uḍaiyār royal house, was the son of Sāmarāja-*mahārāja*. *Sālivāhana-sahāpta* (1755 = 1833 is hinted in the mega compilation, Part III, p. 509) which confirms a date in the early 19th century CE (Kalidos 1994). The STN encompasses the entire range of Hindu iconology, beliefs and rituals.

The authorities cited a wide range of literature dating from the most ancient to the later medieval period. A few are the *vedas*, *itihāsas*, *āgamas*, *tantras*, *upatantras*, *purāṇas*, *upapurāṇas*, *śilpaśāstras*, *dharmasāstras*, *mantras*, *jyotiṣa*, and other liturgical texts. When Raju Kalidos (1994) of the Tamil University took up the *Śaktitattvanidhi* (Part I of the Book), Professor Pierre-Sylvain Filliozat extended a helping hand by reading the translated material, comparing it with the Pune edition in *devanāgarī*. The present article is a direct extract from the original, reprinted in 2007.

The STN consists of nine *nidhis* (treasures) on *ślokas* for *dhyāna* (meditation). Encompassing the entire range of Indian iconography, Part IV deals with ‘Brahmatattvanidhi’ that we elaborate (cf. Santhana-Lakshmi-Parthiban 2014: 72). The divinities enumerated in the ‘Brahmatattvanidhi’ are listed hereunder in the numerical order followed in the STN (vol. I, 4th *nidhi*), mainly highlighting the *nāmas*. However, the numerical order is shifted to suit thematic categories (e.g. 31, 43-44, 71-72). The relevant *śloka* numbers are given in box parentheses. The original essay, circa 15,000 words with 18 illustrations, is abated. The *nāma-rūpa* deserves a better focus because they may not be popular with scholars working on South Asian iconology. Pioneering authorities, e.g. Wilkins (1882/2000), Winternitz (1910/1977), and Dowson (1928/1998) have detailed mythologies. Rao (1914) and Sastri (1916) elaborated on the historical iconographies, Kalidos (1989) concentrating on the wood-carved imageries in *tērs* (cf. Fig. 1). By the way, we strive to prove *viśva-mārga* (Universal Harmony) is rooted in folk maturing in classical art.

Brahmatattva Imageries

Brahmā-Caturmukha is *caturbhujā*, seated in *padmāsana*, the eyes closed in meditation, and of *pāṭalavarṇa*. Usually, he carries the *akṣamālā* and *kamaṇḍalu* in *parahastas* [1]. Sarasvatī is his *patnī* who is *caturbhujā*, standing *samapāda*, *saumyamukha* and white-hued [2]. Ādhyā-Brahmā is *saumyarūpa*, *caturbhujā*, seated in *padmāsana* on *ratha* pulled by seven swans. He puts on *kṛṣṇājina* (for iconographic terms see Liebert 1986 and Rajarajan et al. 2017a). A *vidvān* or *ācārya*, he is of *sakala-lakṣaṇa* and *sāntasvarūpa* [3]. Lokapāla-Brahmā is the *lokadeva* or Jagatpati (Cosmic Lord), *caturbhujā*, shining as *Sūrya-[maṇḍala]* [4]. Prajāpati-Brahmā is posted on *hamsavāhana*, He should not be *caturmukha*. Sāvitrī is on his left lap [5]. They make up the *pañca-Brahmās* (Kalidos 2006: IV, Part II, 133-34). Vidhi-Brahmā is in the form of *Sūrya*, *dvi* or

daśa hastas [6]. Viśvakarma-Brahmā is *caturmukha*, *caturbhujā*, and *catuspāda* seated on *padmāsana* [7].

Nava-Prajāpatis are *mānasaputras* of Brahmā (Rajajaran 2019: 6), the nine progenitors of the *sthāvara* and *jaṅgama vargas* [8-16]. The names are Marīci (hue: *svarṇa-varṇa*), Aṅgiras (*svarṇa*), Atri (*nīla*), Pulastya (*svarṇa*), Pulaha (*nīla*), Kratu (red), Kardama (*sindura*), Kaśyapa (*svarṇa*), and Dakṣa (*nīla*). The common attributes are *jaṭāmaṇḍala*, *patravastra* (or *kṛṣṇājina*), *kamaṇḍalu*, *japamālā*, and *jaṭādhara*.

Sapta-Ṛṣis are Gautama (*patnī* Ahalyā), Bharadvāja, Viśvāmitra, Kaśyapa (*patnīs* Aditi, Kadrū [mother of snakes] and Vinatā [mother of birds, e.g., Garuḍa, Chandramohan 2008], Jamadagni (*patnī* Reṇukā, son Paraśurāma), Vasiṣṭha (*patnī* Arundhadī - Dowson 1998: 339-42, Rajajaran 2019: 5-6, fig. 7), and Atri (*patnī* Anasūyā) [17-24]. The attributes are the same as the Prajāpatis.¹ The *ṛṣis* are *sāntasvarupa*, professors of Cosmic Harmony.

Dharmadevatās are Jñāna, Vairāgya and Aiśvarya [25]. The Dharma *abhimāna-devatās* are Yama (south), Vāyu (northwest), Īśāna (northeast) and Indra (east) that come under *dikpālakas* (cf. Wessels-Mevissen 2001) [26]. Adharma is Ajñāna (fickleness and poverty) in human form [27]. Adharmādi-abhimāna-devatās are Nairṛti, Durgā, Kāma and Rudra [28]. Puṇya-Puruṣa is golden hued [29]. Pāpa-Puruṣa is the *svarūpa* of *brahmahatti* that kills *brāhmaṇas* and *go-[hatya]* of *pañcamahāpātahas* [30]. Dharmasāstra-svarūpa is white, *sāntarūpa* and takes the *kucaṣana* (cf. *kuśa* grass, *kuca* “planet Mars” Liebert 1986: 144). He holds a *japamālā* of pearls and balance (metaphor for judging right and wrong - Kalidos 1989: 296) [61]. Dharmasāstrābhimāni Dharmapuruṣa-svarūpa is *caturmukha*, *caturbhujā* and *catuspāda*. White-hued, he puts on white garments [62].

Ṛgveda-svarūpa-puruṣa is *dvibhujā*, white, and of the donkey-face. He holds the *japamālā* (Kalidos 2012: fig. 19) [32]. *Ṛgveda-patnī* is Sāmidevī graced with the face of peahen [36]. Yajurveda-svarūpa-puruṣa ' is yellow-hued, and goat-faced. He takes the *japamālā* and *vajrāyudha* [33]. 'Sruk' is his *patnī* [37]. Sāmaveda-svarūpa is of horse-face, and *nīlotpala*-hue. His two hands hold the rosary and full-pitcher [34]. Sāmaveda-*patnī* is Guhūdevī. White-hued, she holds a parrot and a bunch of paddy crops [38]. Atharvaṇaveda-svarūpa is monkey-faced [35]. Atharvaṇaveda-

¹ Bhṛgu and Agastya added to the list (Basham 1971: 155).

patnī is Samidh. She is boar-faced. Golden-hued and *caturbhujā*, she takes *sruk*, *sruva*, *padma* and *kumbha* [39]. The *gotra* [g] and Atidevatās of the *Vedas* are *R̥g Ātreya-g* - Soma, *Yajūr Kaśyapa-g* - Rudra, *Sāma Bharadvāja-g* - Indra, and *Atharvaṇa Vaitāna-g* – Brahmā [40]. The *Vedas* and *vedāṅgas* are again discussed in STN (8th *nidhi* 24-31). *Vedaṣaṭaṅgābhīmāni-devatā-svarūpa* are divinities of the six *aṅgas* of the *Veda*, viz., *sikṣa*, *chhandas*, *vyākaraṇa*, *nirukta*, *jyotiṣa* and *kalpa* (ceremonial). The *svarūpas* of the *vedāṅgas* are respectively *Sikṣādevī* (*abhimāni-Prajāpati*), *Chhandas-devatā* (-Aditi), *Vyākaraṇa-puruṣa* (-Sarasvatī), *Nirukta-puruṣa* (-Varuṇa), *Jyotiṣa-puruṣa* (-Hari) and *Kalpa-puruṣa* (-Brahmā) [45-56].

Āyurveda-svarūpa (medicinal science) is monkey-faced and yellow-hued. He takes the *japamālā* and *amṛtakalaśa* [41]. *Dhanvantarī* is the presiding God of *Āyurveda* (*āyus* “[long] life”). *Nīlavarṇa*, he is *sakalalakṣaṇa*, graced with *sakalābharaṇas* [42]. Another version says he is the annihilator of all ailments, *sarvaroha* and offers *kṣema* (“comfort, peace, happiness” Apte 1990: 405).

Brahmāstra-svarūpa is yellow-hued called *Bhagaḷāmukha* (of auspicious face). *Brahmāstra* is a terror to terror-mongers [31]. *Dhanurveda-svarūpa* is sparrow-headed, and the mane is ochre-hued. He holds the *dhanus* and *bāṇa* [43]. *Dhanurvedābhīmāni* is Indra [44]. *Pāśupatāstra-svarūpa* is white-graced with a serpent face [71], cf. *Ketu*, the *grahadevatā* (Santhana-Lakshmi-Parthiban 2019: fig. 6). He holds a noose and vessel in his hands. He wears *vyāgraśarmaraḥ*. *Pāśuptāstra-abhimāni* is *Rudra-svarūpa Parameśvara*. Five-faced, each face is illuminated with three eyes [72].

Mīmāṃsā-śāstra-svarūpa (“Enquiry”) is beaming as *Somakīrti* (the Moon). White-hued, she takes the *japamālā* and *amṛtaghaṭa*. The *abhimāni-devatā* is Soma (Moon) who rides a chariot driven by ten horses (Rajajaran 2015: pl. 157) [57-58]. *Nyāya-śāstra-svarūpa* is lion-faced, holding *japamālā* and *dvaja* in two hands. *Vāyu* is the *abhimāni-devatā*, seated on an antelope [59-60] (Kalidos 1989: pl. 74).

*Purāṇa*²-*svarūpa -puruṣa* is pale yellow or white as the *campaka* (*Gloriosa superba*) flower. The face is a parrot (cf. *Śuka-brahmaṛṣi*). Decorated with *nānābharaṇas*, the *dvibhujas* show *japamālā* and *abhaya*. *Purāṇas* are immoral preaching *dharma*, *nīti* and *śānti* [63]. *Purāṇa-devatā*

² See Winternitz (1977: 453); old, belonging to halcyon days, primeval, ancient or legendary history; *Viṣṇu* is *Purāṇa-Puruṣa*.

is Svayambhuva-Manu (infra) [64]. Itihāsa-svarūpa -puruṣa is of the hue of *kuśa*-grass (*Poa cynosoroides*). He holds the *japamālā* and *pūrṇaghāṭa*, decorated with *padmābharāṇa* (sea of lotuses) [65]. Itihāsa-devatā is Prajāpati-Brahmā (supra) seated on *haṃsavāhana* [66].

Bharataśāstra³-svarūpa (*nāṭyaśāstra*) is *rajanimaya* (*rajaniḥ* “night, turmeric, the moon”, “thief” Apte 1990: 910), fitted with the face of an antelope. Three-eyed, s/he takes the *japamālā* and *triśūla*. The *Cilappatikāram* (*kātai* 3) presents minute regulations of *nāṭyaśāstra* [67] (Jeyapriya 2018: II, 545-51). Bharata-śāstrābhīmāṇi-devatā is Umāmaheśvara, the presiding divinity of *nāṭyaśāstra* (Kalidos 2006: II, pl. LXXXII.1, LXXXV.1, XC.1, XCVI.2) is white. He is in *sukāsana* with Umā posed in *lalitāsana* mode. The Lord’s four hands show *ṭaṅka*, *mṛga*, *abhaya* and *varada*. Umā is *dvibhuja* fitted with *nīlotphala* and *varada* [68].

Pāñcarātra-śāstra-svarūpa is personification of *Pāñcarātrāgama*. White-hued Puruṣa-svarūpa (cf. the *Puruṣasūktam*), he is seated on *vṛṣabha-vāhana*. He holds the *japamālā* and *hala* in two hands graced with *vanamālā*. It seems the divinity is an embodiment of the Hindu Triad; *hala* and *vanamālā* Vaiṣṇava, *vṛṣabha* Śaiva and *japamālā* Brahmā [69]. Pāñcarātrābhīmāṇi Saṃkarṣaṇa⁴-svarūpa is of the same mould as Vāsudeva. White-hued, he puts on blue garments. *Musala* (*muśala* or *mūśala*) and *hala* are in *parahastas*. The left forehand carries the *dhanus-śārṅga* [70].

Patañjala-śāstra-svarūpa denotes the *Yogasūtra* of sage Patañjali (c. 2nd century BCE - Basham 1971: 328), the divinity who cultivated *yoga*. This divinity is snake-faced, graced with *japamālā* and *pādukas* [73]. Patañjali-devatā Ananta-svarūpa is of the hue of tender mango leaves (pale green), otherwise the *gomūtram*, one among the *pañcagavyas* (Apte 1990: 640, Liebert 1986: 208). His beard and moustache are yellow. His eyes are lotus flowers, *puṇḍarīkākṣa* [74].

Sāṅkhya-śāstra-svarūpa is *babhrū* “tawny-reddish-brown or brown” (Apte 1990: 332, 793, Monier-Williams 2005: 721). Decorated with shining *kunḍalas*, his attributes are *japamālā* and

³ The *Nāṭyaśāstra* of Bharata is perhaps the *Nāṭṭiyanaṇṇūl* (Good Book on Dance) noted in the *Cilappatikāram* (3.40), c. 200-450 CE.

⁴ Saṃkarṣaṇa is among the *vyūha-catuṣṭaya-mūrti* (STN 2.43), i.e., the *caturvyūhas* that includes Vāsudeva, Pradyumna and Aniruddha.

daṇḍa [75]. Sāṅkhya-sāstrābhīmāni Kapila is illuminating as 1000 suns, his mien brilliant as Sūrya. Sāntasvarūpa, his emblems are *jñāna* and *abhaya –mudrās* [76].

Catusṣaṣṭikalā “Sixty-four Arts”⁵ are listed beginning with the *vedas*, *vedāṅgas*, *itihāsas*, *āgamas*, *alaṅkāra-śāstra*, *kāmasāstra*, *svara-śāstra*, *aśvalakṣaṇa*, *gajalakṣaṇa* (Sheshadri 2017, today *gohatya* is an art), wood-architecture, *citra-[lakṣaṇa]*, *aṣṭasihhis*, *indrajāla*, including gambling, theft (*coraśāstra* Sheshadri 2015, cf. Rajarajan 2016) and so on [77].

Pañcabhūta-svarūpa are Pṛthvi, Ap, Tejas, Vāyu and Ākāśa. Pṛthvī/Bhū Devī is white/bright (*śuklavarna*), decorated with *divyābharaṇas*, *caturbhujā*, *sāntirūpa* and puts on shining garments. She is seated on *dikgajas* [78]. Apdevatās give life to *jīvātmas/jaṅgamas* [79]. Tejodevatā-svarūpa is Agni of *svarna-varṇa* [80]. His *patnī* is Svāhādevī. Vāyudevatā is seated on a prancing antelope [81]. Ākāśadevatā is graced with *nīlavastra*, and *sakalābharaṇas* [82].

Under Daśadik-svarūpa the divinities enumerated are Pūrva-(*dik*) [83], Āgneya- [84], Dakṣiṇa- [85], Nairṛti- [86], Varuṇa- [87], Vāyu- [88], Uttara- [89], Īśāna- [90], Ūrdhvadik-(*ākāśa*) [91], and Adodik (Bhūdevī) [92]. The Aṣṭadikpālakas enumerated in detail are Indra-east (consort Śāśidevī), Agni-southeast (Svāhā and Svadhā), Yama-south (Ilā), Nairṛti-southwest (Kālīkā), Varuṇa-west (Padminī), Vāyu-northwest (Mohinī), Kubera-north (Siddhirinī) and Īśāna-northeast (Gaurīdevī) [96-103].

Aṣṭanāga-svarūpa snakes are Ananta, Vāśuki, Dakṣa, Kārkoṭaka, Padma, Mahāpadma, Śāṅkhapāla and Kuḷika [93]. The *nāga* totem is common to almost all religions of Indian origin. The snakes are brought under *caturvarṇas*, e.g. Ananta *brāhmaṇa*, Vāśuki *kṣatriya*, Dakṣa *vaiśya*, and Padma *śūdra*. Whether *brāhmaṇa* or *śūdra*, snakes are fatal, either anaconda or cobra.

Aṣṭa-Vasus were natural phenomena during the Vedic time, the eight Vasus are attendants of Indra, they are Āpa (water), Dhruva (polestar, grandson of Svayambhūvamanu infra), Soma (moon), Dhara (earth), Anila (wind), Anala (fire), Prabhāsa (dawn) and Pratyūṣa (night). They are children of Aditi (Dowson 1998: 342). The order followed in STN (citing the *Śaivāgama*, *Varṇam*,

⁵ Devī is ‘Catuṣṣaṣṭikalāmayī’ (LSN-236), Catusṣaṣṭikalādevī is a form of Sarasvatī (‘Śāradārādhyā’ LSN-123), the sixty-four arts are listed in the *Kāmasūtra* (Burton 1994: 15-18, Upadhyaya 1970: 76-78).

Kāranāgama) is Dhruva [104], Advāra/Dhara [105], Soma [106], Ap/Āpa [107], Anila [108], Anala [109], Pratyūṣa [110], and Prabhāsa [111]. The attributes are uniformly *dvibhuja*, *varadamudrā* and *saumya* flowering face.

Sapta-auṣadhas are the seven elixirs of immortality, the manifestations of Vāyu.⁶ They are Āvahavāyu [112], Vivaha offers *aiśvarya* [113], Udhvaḥ is tempest [114], Samvaḥ the *mandamāruta* (inebriating breeze) [115], Nivaḥ same as Udhvaḥ [116], Pratihūlah “anti/negative” (opposite of *anuhūla* “pro/positive”) [117], and Vyavaḥ is *prāṇa* and *apāna* that is *auṣadha-vāyu* [118].

Sapta-Maruts (Vedic storm gods - Dowson 1998: 203) are *vāyus*, each consisting of seven variants (7 x 7), a total of forty-nine. 120. The forty-nine are given each a name, e.g., *prāṇa-1*, *apāna-2*, *nāga-6*, *kūrma-8*, *devadatta-9*, *śambhu-13*, *āvaha-17*, *śaṅkha-18*, *kāla-19*, *śibhi-27*, *rakta-29*, *kṛṣṇa-30*, *siddha-35*, *saumya-38*, *maṇḍuka*⁷-43 (“frog” cf. Vajracharya 2013), *bhūma-44*, *kapi-45*, *jaṭa-47*, and so on [119]. They share common characteristics, shining as Sūrya, decorated with *krīṭa-hāra-keyūra-kaṭaka*, and are the aide de camp of Indra.

Daśa-Viśvadevatā-svarūpa are Kratu, Dakṣa, Vasū, Satya, Kāla, Kāma, Turi (sic?), Locana, Purūravas, Ārdirava (sic?). They carry *dhanus* and *bāṇa* (white) [121].

Sapta-samudra-svarūpa is seven the seven oceans (Sandahl 2012). They are Lavaṇa (salt water) [122], Ikṣu (syrup, sugarcane-juice) [123], Sura (wine) [124], Sarpis (ghee) [125], Dadhi (curds) [126], Kṣīra (milk) [127], and Suddhodaka (*svādūda*[ka] “sweet, pleasant” [128]). The iconographies are elaborated (Rajarajan 2019a).

⁶ According to the traditional Indian medicinal science (*siddha* or *āyurveda*) good health is intact when *pittam* (bile), *vāyu* (popularly “gas”, gastric diagnoses) and *kapam* (phlegm) are in proportion. Vāyu is the overlord of health. Wind pollution in metropolitan cities, now curtailed by lockdowns all over the world due to ‘Korona’.

⁷ ‘Maṇḍūka’ is a *mahaṛṣi* accommodated in the holy of the holies of the Tāṭikkompu temple of the Nāyaka period (Gopalakrishnan 1996). Frogs are much less respected in Tamil tradition. The proverb is *nuṇalum taṇ vāyāl keṭum* “The frog is self-ruined by its tongue”.

Aṣṭa-Nadī-svarūpa are the eight River goddesses [129]⁸, *dvibhuja* holding the *kumbha* and *varuṇapāśa*, and seated on *makara-vāhana* (cf. Jayapal 2010: 114-24, Kalidos 2012: fig. 21). They are Gaṅgā [130], Yamunā [131], Godāvarī [132], Kṛṣṇā [133], Revā [134], Tāpī or Mahānadī [135], Veṇī (means “river”) or Narmadā [136], and Sarasvatī or Praveṇī [137]. Sarasvatī is subterranean, believed to meet the Gaṅgā and the Yamunā at Prayāgaḥ. She assures *maṅgaḷas* “holiness” and *ānanda* “bliss”.

Parjanya-svarūpa is the cloud graced with the faces of three elephants [138], cf. Indra’s *samvartaka* cloud in the *Bhāgavata Purāṇa* (Kalidos 2006: I, 44), the presiding God of *divyadeśa*-Mōkūr is ‘Kālamegha’ Perumāḷ (Rajaraman et al. 2017a: 833). *Parjanya* (rain cloud, God of rain; Apte 1990: 673) is the life-giving source of *sakala-jīvarāsis*. Āṅṭāl in *Tiruppāvai* (3-4) invokes Viṣṇu to shower for the prosperity of the worlds.

Aśvinidevatās are the twin, Nāsatya and Dasra. Experts in medicinal science (cf. Norelius 2017) put on yellow garments, yellow wreaths and the complexion yellow [139].

Kāmadhenu (*Kāmaduh*, Śavalā and Surabhi) is the “Cow of Plenty” [140]. She is the mother of Nandinī. The Cosmic Mother, Viṣṇu, is the zoomorphic Cow (Rajaraman et al. 2017b: pl. 69).

Dvādaśa-āyudhas are twelve choicest weapons, the personified are *vajra*, *śakti*, *daṇḍa*, *khaḍga*, *pāśa*, *aṅkuśa*, *gadā*, *triśūla*, *cakra*,⁹ *padma* et alii [141] (L’Hernault 1990, Giuliano 2001, Jeyapriya 2004). The personified weapons may be masculine, feminine or *napuṃsaka* (Santhana-Lakshmi-Parthiban 2014: 81).

Śakti-traya makes up the trio that is Prabhuśakti (Viṣṇu, Śiva, Indra or the Triad) [142], Mantraśakti (prayer, magic, incantation, spell) [143] and Utsāhaśakti [144] (“effort, exertion, perseverance, power of a ruler” Apte 1990: 262, popularly “exhilaration”).

⁸ Ancient chronicles speak of *Sapta-Sindhava*, “seven rivers”. Dowson (1998: 281) cites a passage from the *Eneid* (ix, 30): “Ceus septem surgens sedatis amnibus altus/ Per tacitum Ganges”.

⁹ Vaiṣṇava tradition talks of *pañcāyudhas/aimpaṭai* (Rajaraman et al. 2017a: 23), viz., *Sudarśana* (disc), *Kaumodakī* (mace/club), *Śārṅga* (bow), *Nandaka* (sword) and *Pāñcajanya* (conch).

Upāyadevatās are *Sāma* (conciliation or negotiation) [145], *dāna* (bribery¹⁰) [146], *bheda* (showing dissension) [147] and *daṇḍa* (capital punishment) [148] are the four *upāyas* (stratagem, expedient) to overcome an enemy or get a job done hook or crook.

Fourteen-Manus are Patriarchs during each *kalpa* of the Hindu cosmological scale of infinity, Viśvadevatās of *viśvakāla*. Manu denotes “man, mankind” (*Ṛgveda*), thinking, wise, “thinking creature (?)”, “Man par excellence” (Monier-Williams 2005: 784). The Manus are Svāyambhuvamanu-*kṣatriya* [149], Svārosiṣamanu-*brāhmaṇa* [150], Uttamamanu-*kṣatriya* [151], Tāmasamanu-*kṣatriya* [152], Raivatamanu-*kṣatriya* [153], Saṣūṣamanu-*brāhmaṇa* [154], Vaivasvatamanu-*kṣatriya/brāhmaṇa (pratiloma)* [155], Sūrya-sāvarṇimanu son of Sūrya (cf. Karṇa) [156], Dakṣa-sarvāṇimanu-*kṣatriya* [157], Brahma-sarvāṇimanu-*brāhmaṇa* [158], Dharma-sarvāṇimanu-*kṣatriya* [159], Rudra-sarvāṇimanu-*kṣatriya* [160], Veda sarvāṇimanu-*brāhmaṇa* [161], and Indra-sarvāṇimanu-*kṣatriya* [162].

Navacirañjīvis (*cirañjīva* “long lived” Apte 1990: 465) means nine immortal heroes. They are Aśvatthāma-*brāhmaṇa* [163], Bali-*dānava* king [164], Vyāsa (*kṣatriya-niṣāda pratilomajā*) [165], Hanūmān-*vānara* [166], Vibhīṣaṇa *rākṣasa-rāja* [167], Kṛpa-*ṛṣi* [168], Paraśurāma-*brāhmaṇa* [169], under *daśāvātāra* of Viṣṇu, Prahlāda *daitya* [170], and Mārkaṇḍeya [171] (Parthiban 2019: figs. 1-3).

Daśa-munis are common in Sanskrit (sage, devotee, ascetic) and Tamil (*muṇi, iruṭi-ṛṣi*). The ten *munis* are Marīci, Atri, Aṅgiras, Bṛhaspati, Pulastya, Pulaha, Kratu (his wife Sammatī was mother of 60,000 *vālikihilya-ṛṣis*, authors of a *saṃhita* STN 8.56), Vasiṣṭha, Bhṛgu, and Nārada [172]. Uniformly *dvibhuja*, they take the *yogaḍaṇḍa* and *kamaṇḍalu* (Rajajaran 2019a: figs. 3-7).

Twelve more *ṛṣis* are brought under Bhṛgu-*gaṇa* and ten more under Aṅgiro-*gaṇa*. They are *sveta* (white) and *pīta* (yellow) *varṇa* respectively. The Bhṛgugaṇas are Bhṛgu, Vāmadeva, Bhruvana, Bhāvana, Sūjaniya, Kratu, Sarvasvasū, Vyaśṛda, Pravāsa, Avyaya and Dakṣa [173]. They are privileged to perform *yajñas* for *devas* and *brāhmaṇas*. Two higher and lower grade *brāhmaṇas* perform the *anyeṣṭi* (funeral rituals) for the *brāhmaṇas* and others, which is a living

¹⁰ From the ‘Vedānta’ (of Kāviri and Tūttukkuṭi) to ‘Bofers’ (warplanes), this is the most powerful weapon to massacre innocent people.

tradition. The Aṅgirogaṇa *munis* (*gaṇa*, *munigaṇa*) are of the same mould as the previous. They are Ātma, Āyus, Mana¹¹, Dakṣa, Pādaprabha, Haviṣya, Kaviṣṭha, Kratu, Satya and Devala [174].

Śāstrābhīmāṇi-devatā [see 45-56 above] are *sikṣa* - Prajāpati, *kalpa* - Brahmā, *vyākaraṇa* - Sarasvatī, *nirukta* - Varuṇa, *chhandas* - Aditi and Agni, and *jyotiṣa* - Bhagavān Viṣṇu, *Mīmāṃsā* - Soma, *Nyāyāsāstra* - Vāyu, *Dharmaśāstra* - Dharmadevatā, *Purāṇas* - Manu, *Itihāsas* - Prajāpati, *dhanurveda* - Indra, *āyurveda* - Dhanvantari, *miśravedas* (*miśra* “mixed”) - Mahādeva, *niruktaśāstra* (cf. *nirukta* “defined” -*vedāṅga* above) - Maheśvara, *Pāñcarātra*¹² - Saṃkarṣaṇa, *pāśupata* - Rudra, *Patañjala-yoga* - Ananta, *sāṅkhya* - Kapila, *arthaśāstras* - *lokaguru*-Kāmadeva, other *śāstra*-makers.

Yakṣa-svarūpas are the *atidevatās* of *guṇas*, brought under *sattva*-Viṣṇu, *rājasa*-Brahmā and *tāmasa*-Śiva. Levitating in the sky, they are armed with *khadga* and *kheṭaka*. They assure all *subhamaṅgaḷas* [175]. They are normally *punyajanas* and occasionally treated imps. Dowson (1998: 373) adds, “It is a *yakṣa* in whose mouth Kālidāsa places his poem *Meghadūta* (Cloud Messenger).”

Viśvakarma-svarūpa is the architect of the gods. *Sakalalakṣaṇa*, he is graced with a moustache and beard. *Dvibhuja*, takes a cutting *takṣaka* instrument in one hand [176]. He is five-faced (Rajarajan 2006: II, pl. 107).

The book concludes with the general observation that *śāstra* and *kāvya* are on the same plane as the *vedas*. All make up the Hindu Scripture (cf. Scialpi 2012). The Hindu scriptures are many-faceted in several languages, and Sanskrit or Tamil is not the end. Tiruvaḷḷuvar in *Tirukkuraḷ*, omits *mokṣa* and deals with *aram-dharma*, *poruḷ-artha* and *iṅpam-kāma*. If these three are nurtured righteously, *vītu-mokṣa* is assured, cf. the *Cīriya* and *Periya tirumaṭals* of Tirumaṅkai Āḷvār (Rajarajan et al. 2017: IV, 2232-86).

¹¹ Several names are new to specialists in iconology. Ātma, Āyus and Mana seem to be personifications of “Soul” (Self), “Life” and “Mind”.

¹² *Pāñcarātra* consists of 108 *saṃhitās*. Vaikhānasa is unnoticed.

Summation

The subject under examination is a clear pointer to the Viśvadevatās that encompass the cosmos. Virāṭ Puruṣa is the creator and sustainer, finally, everything dissolved and absorbed in baby-Kṛṣṇa, Vaṭapatrasāyī (Parthiban 2019: figs. 6, 9). Brahmā, Indra, ṛṣis or munis are viśālakāla's ephemeral entities. The Lord (Puruṣa, Brahman) and His Feminine (Puruṣikā, Prakṛti, Devī) are the Virāṭ. This is the underlying philosophy of 'Brahmatattva'. Sociologically, Brahmā and brāhmaṇa are on equal terms, that are hidden rationalism shrouded in sociological stratagem. The unattached 'Universal Man' is pulinda (Kalidos 2010: 78) or kirāta-priya. Scholars of the yester generation spoke in terms of "inferior deities" (Wilkins 2000: 363), "demigods" (ibidem 411) and "miscellaneous minor deities" (ibidem 473), "miscellaneous deities" (Sastri 1916: 235-72), "demigods" (Rao 1999: 547-70), and "Brahmā and minor gods" (Kalidos 1989: chap. VII). In fact, gods are gods. They are at a higher plane, the interlinked Śiva-Gaṅgā (River), Viṣṇu-Garuḍa (Bird), Dakṣiṇa/Vaṭapatrasāyī (Tree), Buddha-Nāga (Serpent) and so on. The grassroots of Indian religious culture are in unrecorded folk, including oral thoughts. Modern Hinduism is a syncretism of folk and elite. The so-called higher tradition is rooted in folk or literary works whose authors are unknown (Parthiban 2019a, cf. Göttet 2016). The *Gītā* and Māṇikkavācakar (*Civapurāṇam* ll. 26-30) find the Man in Dio-Kṛṣṇa and Dio-bambino in Arjuna, the Nara-Nārāyaṇa¹³ seated atop the Himālayan peak, Badarīnātha. Simply, this is the universal vision of 'Brahmatattva'.

To quote the *Gītā* (10.21-38), Viṣṇu is the Ādityas, Sūrya, Marīci, Moon, *Sāma-gāṇa*, Indra, *manas* (mind), *cetana* (instinct), Śaṅkara, Kubera, Agni, Meru, Bṛhaspati, Skanda, ocean, Bhṛgu, *Ekākṣara* (Om), *Japa*, Himālaya, *aśvattha*, Nārada, Citraratha, Kapila-*muni*, Uchhaiśravas (Rajarajan 2009: pl. VI a-b), Airāvata (Rajarajan & Jeyapriya 2013: pl. 15), the King, *vajra*, Kāmadhenu (*go* "cow"), Kandarpa-Manmatha, *sarpa*-Vāśuki, *nāga*-Ananta, Varuṇa, *pitṛ*-Aryamā, Yama, Prahlāda, Kāla, *siṃha*, Garuḍa, Vāyu, Rāma, *makara*, Jāhnavī/Gaṅgā, first-middle-last (*ādiḥ-madhyam-antaḥ*), *ātma*vidya, *vādaḥ*, Gāyatri, *mārgaśīrṣa*, Vasanta-*ṛtu*, *sattvaṃ*, *vṛṣṇi*-Vāsudeva, Pāṇḍava Dhanañjaya/Dharmarāja, *muni*-Vyāsa, Śukra, the Scepter, *Nīti*, *Mauna*, and

¹³ Cf. Sūrya-Nārāyaṇa, Sūrya or Āditya is one of the earliest divinities, the warmth-giving natural force (cf. 'Agnimārga' in Álvarez 2015-16: 19-21), deified in most archaic cults.

tattva-jñāna. Where do I find the grass-roots, the trunk and branches of the *vrkṣa*-Jagatpati? The *Gītā* (14.1) says,

ūrdhvamūlamadhaḥśākamaśvatthamprāhūravyyam|

cchandāmsiyasyaparṇāniyastamvedasavedavit||

“The banyan (*aśvattha*) roots (folk) are up and the boughs (classical Hinduism) underneath that which they say are non-decaying *samsāra*. The sages know the roots of the *veda* and its branches.” (parentheses mine, cf. Scialpi 2012).

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